

Simulating Quantum Chemistry on Heterogeneous Architectures

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Abstract—Simulating chemistry with quantum mechanical accuracy is a challenging task, while at the same time crucial to describing certain molecular interactions. On a classical machine, the scaling of quantum chemistry methods ranges from cubic for popular but less accurate methods to exponential for the highest quality methods. Quantum computers may be able to reduce the exponential scaling for high-accuracy methods, but while current quantum devices remain noisy, it is important to fully leverage modern high performance computing hardware. Doing so will enable pushing past present limits to study or even design new chemistry. In this work we present efforts to scale quantum chemistry simulations to heterogeneous HPC systems, simulate quantum circuits efficiently on classical hardware, and provide an outlook on hybrid quantum/classical approaches.

Index Terms—quantum chemistry, quantum computing, tensor networks, GPU, QPU

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum chemistry has connections to applications in chemical/materials design and drug discovery as well as to technologies like quantum computing and machine learning, which could be leveraged to accelerate quantum chemistry. At the heart of these connections is an increase in high-performance computing (HPC) power, largely driven by accelerators like GPUs. Quantum chemistry can be a tool, built on the engine of cutting-edge computers, to help address our world’s current and future problems ranging from human health to materials for sustainability. To this end, improvements to the tool—improving how quantum chemistry methods are formulated and implemented to use current and emerging computer power—are crucial. Fig. 1 shows a schematic of quantum chemistry as a central tool which can incorporate modern computing power (e.g. HPC and quantum computing) to drive applications research, even closing the feedback loop with materials design for more efficient computing.

In this work, we present distinct efforts to (1) accelerate and distribute quantum chemistry simulation for HPC and (2) simulate quantum circuits using tensor network methods adapted from quantum chemistry and physics. We conclude by discussing the need for hybrid quantum/classical approaches to leverage near-term quantum devices.

II. QUANTUM CHEMISTRY AT SCALE: DISTRIBUTED, GPU-ACCELERATED SIMULATIONS

The fast evaluation of electronic structure is crucial for studying the dynamics of molecular systems, for reaction

Fig. 1. Quantum chemistry as a central tool connecting modern computing technologies to applications in materials design and drug discovery. Dashed lines represent feedback connections.

discovery, or for generating high quality training data for machine learning models of chemistry. While electronic structure calculations are expensive (relative to force-field or ML models), they are also well-suited for parallelization, as the ratio of compute intensity to input/output data is high. Efforts to parallelize and scale quantum chemistry codes have a long history, but in the past decade there has been considerable success adapting quantum chemistry algorithms to take advantage of advances in graphics cards [1]–[6]. While a single GPU can provide one or two orders of magnitude speedup over CPUs for electronic structure problems [7], modern HPC systems are increasingly heterogeneous, with multiple nodes which may contain different types of processors and different architectures. This heterogeneity presents challenges to the quantum chemistry community, as codes will need to be adapted to new architectures and scaled to larger systems.

To address this challenge, we develop a multi-node, multi-GPU implementation [8] of the electron-repulsion integrals (ERIs)—the computational bottleneck for a popular family of quantum chemistry methods including density functional theory (DFT). The number of ERIs scales formally as $O(N^4)$, where N is the number of atom-centered Gaussian basis functions used to represent the chemical system, but can be effectively reduced to $O(N^2)$ with screening techniques. ERIs are used to compute Coulomb (J) and exchange (K) matrices, primitives in many electronic structure methods [5]. Our approach uses the task-based parallel programming

Fig. 2. (a) Regent approach: a mapper abstracts memory management from the programmer and code can be executed on heterogeneous configurations. (b) Self-consistent field (SCF) iteration times and speedup for Regent code computing ERIs (J and K) for the entire green fluorescent protein (RHF/6-31G) distributed across three nodes and multiple GPUs (NVIDIA Tesla K80s, XStream GPU compute cluster at the Stanford Research Computing Facility).

language Regent [9], [10]. Code written in Regent appears sequential (and is easy to develop and maintain), but the runtime system and mapper distribute tasks in parallel at runtime to whichever processors are provided by the user. The same piece of code is thereby hardware agnostic—it can be run on a variety of architectures and configurations (see Fig. 2a). Fig. 2b shows the execution time and parallel speedup for computing J and K matrices for the entire green fluorescent protein molecule which contains over 3000 atoms—a very large system for quantum chemistry standards—distributed across multiple nodes and multiple GPUs. The GPU code is 100-400x faster than the generated CPU code, consistent with previous comparisons to CPU-based codes [7].

ERIs depend on the angular momentum of the Gaussian basis functions used to describe the electronic orbitals of a molecule, i.e. s , p , d , f , etc. ERIs can be computed via recursion formulas, which lend themselves to metaprogramming techniques. We use expressive metaprogramming features in Regent to generate GPU code whose performance matches that of hand-optimized CUDA kernels for low angular momenta, but can in addition be extended to high angular momenta [8]. Efficient GPU-accelerated ERI code for f functions will now allow us to study more chemistry, e.g. molecules containing heavier elements like transition metals.

III. QUANTUM CIRCUIT SIMULATION USING TENSOR NETWORK APPROACHES

Quantum computing is a paradigm that has the potential to drastically improve our ability to simulate quantum systems, in the ideal case removing the exponential scaling of high-

accuracy quantum chemistry methods. In the near-term, however, quantum computers will have small numbers of noisy qubits. During this NISQ (noisy intermediate-scale quantum) era, simulators of quantum computers that run on classical machines are important for benchmarking and algorithm development. Simulators built on tensor network approaches represent a quantum state in a compressed form, and therefore present a promising path for simulation on HPC resources [11]. Tensor network approaches arose independently in the quantum physics community (to study quantum many body problems with methods like DMRG [12]) and in the quantum chemistry community (to study the quantum dynamics of small molecules with methods like multi-layer MCTDH [13], [14]).

We introduce QuTree, a C++ library for tree tensor network methods [15], [16]. While tree tensor network methods developed from the MCTDH community and the library supports simulating molecules, QuTree was built to be general purpose and can also be used to simulate quantum circuits. This represents another link in the feedback loop in Fig. 1: quantum chemistry can help us improve quantum computing. We demonstrate QuTree’s performance by simulating 2D random circuits like those used by the Google Quantum AI team to show quantum advantage in 2019 [17]. We show that the library is significantly more performant than the matrix product state (MPS) simulator provided by Qiskit, a popular toolkit for quantum circuit simulation. We go on to simulate a circuit for Shor’s algorithm that factors a 9-bit integer. The simulation includes all gates which would be required on an actual quantum computer [18]. To our knowledge, a simulation at this level of detail has not yet been reported.

IV. OUTLOOK

Quantum chemistry is a central tool that connects modern computing technologies like HPC and quantum computers to applications in chemical and materials design. In our work we show how quantum chemistry methods can be scaled to HPC systems by implementing the computational bottleneck (ERIs) in a language that enables efficient execution on heterogeneous architectures. We discuss how tensor network methods from quantum chemistry can be used to simulate quantum circuits to enable quantum algorithm development in the NISQ era.

While quantum computing is indeed a different paradigm for simulating physical systems, in the context of HPC, quantum devices can be seen as simply more kinds of accelerators (QPUs). With near-term quantum devices, quantum advantage for relevant problems is most likely to be achieved using hybrid quantum/classical approaches, where the computationally intensive portion of the problem is offloaded to a quantum device. Future work will focus on developing a system that enables efficient simulation on heterogeneous hardware including both traditional and quantum accelerators. Pushing the limits of quantum simulation on classical and quantum hardware *together* has the potential to not only accelerate chemical discovery and design, but also inform our understanding of quantum algorithms and help shape the future directions of quantum computing.

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